

Impact of Dalton Plan Instructional Model on Interest in Basic Science among Upper Basic School Students in Kano Metropolis

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Abstract

The study investigates the Impact of Dalton Plan Instructional Model on Interest in Basic Science among Upper Basic School Students in Kano Metropolis. The study was guided by one research objective, corresponding research question and one null Hypothesis. Quasi experimental design was adopted for the study. The population comprised 7850 from 21 public schools. The sampling technique is simple random sample. The sample consisting of 73 randomly selected Upper Basic 2 Students of 38 students for dalton plan instructional method (DPIM) and 35 conventional Lecture method (CLM) students of Basic Science in Kano Metropolis. The instrument for data collection was Basic Science Interest Inventory (BSII). The instrument was validated by experts and subjected to pilot study using Cronbach's Alpha. The reliability coefficient of 0.77 was obtained. Mean and standard deviation statistics was used to answer the research questions. One way analysis of covariance was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 levels of significance. The results of the study revealed that interest rating score of students taught Basic Science concept using Dalton Plan Instructional Model was higher than the students taught using conventional Lecture method in Basic Science. Based on the research finding, it was recommended that Science teachers should employ Dalton Plan Instructional Model as teaching method in Basic Science.

Keywords: Dalton Plan Instructional Model, Interest and Basic Science.

Introduction

Teaching and learning go hand in hand, teaching is the assistance, guidance, direction rendered to learners to discover self, not a mere lip service but most respected profession. The teachings that go on in most of our schools are dominated orally. The teachers are to ensure that teaching method employed is to create fresh environment and interest to the students (Okereke, 2024). Basic Science is a necessity for Science and Technology development in Nigeria. Basic science formally known as Integrated Science is a subject taught in public and private schools at the Upper Basic level in Nigeria.

The reason for teaching Basic Science according to Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2014), is that, it widens the knowledge of the learners which enables them to appreciate the unity among science subjects such as, Agricultural Science, Biology, Chemistry and Physics. National Education Research and Development Council (NERDC, 2007), stipulated that the objectives of the Basic Science curriculum are to enable learners: Develop interest in science; Acquire basic knowledge and skills in science; Apply scientific knowledge and skills to meet societal needs; Take advantage of the numerous career opportunities offered by science; Become prepared for further studies. Therefore, Gambo (2019), was of the view that, the requirements on learners are increasing and one of the necessary abilities is to work well independently as well as in a team. To achieve this target, teachers should use diverse teaching methods, such as, conventional lecture method, cooperative learning, collaboration, discussion, Dalton plan instructional-model, inquiry, reciprocal peer-tutoring, demonstration and many more, among all these, the most widely practiced is conventional lecture method. Udo (2016) is of the opinion that poor

academic performances in Basic Science were partly due to insufficient instructional materials, interest, unqualified/ not subject teachers and ineffective strategies of teaching employed by teachers.

However, Basic Science Student Academic Performance Results from Kano Education Resource Department (KERD) for 2016 – 2022 in Basic Education Certificate Examinations (BECE) as reported by the chief examiner, Basic Science, Kano State. It is in the light of the above that, the present study aims at investigating the impact of Dalton Plan Instructional Model and conventional lecture method on Interest among Upper Basic Students in Basic Science in Kano Metropolis.

Dalton Plan Instructional Model is an organized learning packaged environment which encourages easy access to material representation of a phenomenon, an idea for learners to work/learn with each other at their pace. Parkhurst (2010), Describes, Dalton plan as where students are allowed to work at their own pace and only receive individual help from the teacher (facilitator) when necessary, for this study will be referred to Dalton Plan Instructional Model. There is no formal class instruction, learners draw up their time-tables which they use to explore academic syllabuses through entirely personal efforts. Learners are also encouraged to work together and thereby help one another in the course of their work.

Therefore, Dalton Instructional Model is also known as Dalton laboratory method, because laboratories replace classrooms (Hanior,2017). The classroom is seen as an educational workshop equipped with books, maps, drawings, photographs, and other materials that will enable each student with little assistance as possible, to complete the work which student should do and predict solutions throughout the work so as to improve student interest. In order to improve Interest among Upper Basic Students in Basic Science, this research will investigate the impact of Dalton Instructional Model. Therefore, the impact of Dalton Plan Instructional Model, may establish the potentials inherent in basic science, that such learner will definitely relate better to the subject learning Interest in the Basic Science.

Interest is the kind of awareness preference for understanding the world and acquiring cultural and scientific knowledge. When students are interested in a certain field, they may pay special attention to it, observing carefully, memorizing well and thinking actively. Shehu (2021) states that only by arousing students' interest with various teaching and learning methods we can enhance students' enthusiasm for learning basic science; help them master basic science conceptual knowledge and techniques better, form the scientific spirit and attitude. Therefore, Godpower and Ihenko (2017), says that improved interest will enable upper Basic students to solve problems, think critically, make decisions, find answers, fulfill their curiosity and perform better academically in basic science.

According to Godpower and Ihenko, (2017) the low interest, non-application of science to production activities and insufficient teaching resources and teaching methodology employed by teachers is connected to low academic performance in basic science. However, Nwosu, Ehud and John, (2017) and Samuel (2018) are of the view that these may also affect basic science and technology students' interest and academic performance such as societal misconception of gender role and its impact on technology, absence of practical work in schools.

The problem of students' low interest in Basic Science in upper basic levels in Nigeria has been an educational issue. In solving any problem however, it is proper to understand the causes of such problems. These causes are looked into from several perspectives including the role of the students, teachers, school environment, society, government and so on. Therefore, on this background, the present study investigated the Impact of Dalton Plan Instructional Model on Interest in Basic Science among Upper Basic School Students in Kano Metropolis.

Objective of the Study

The aim of this study was to determine the Impact of Dalton Plan Instructional Model on Interest in Basic Science among Upper Basic School Students in Kano Metropolis. Specifically, the study seeks to investigate the:

1. Impact of Dalton plan instructional Model on interest among upper basic students in Basic Science and those taught using conventional lecture method.

Research Question

The following research question guided the study

1. What is the impact of Dalton plan instructional Model and conventional lecture method on interest among upper basic students when taught Basic Science?

Hypothesis

The following null hypothesis was formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance

1. **H0₁**: There is no significant difference in the mean interest rating score of Dalton plan instructional model and conventional lecture method among upper basic students when taught Basic Science.

Methodology

The study employed quasi experimental design using pretest, posttest non-randomised control group. The population comprised 7850 from 21 public upper basic schools in Kano State. The sample of the study was 73 Upper Basic Science 2 students (38 students in DPIM (treatment group) and 35 students in CLM (control group) of two intact classes selected from the 7 coeducational schools in Kano Metropolis. The selection of the school and intact class was done using simple random sampling technique by balloting. The instrument for the study was Basic Science Interest Inventory (BSII) made up of 20 items construct in 5-points scale, adapted from Wong and Wong (2019) whose study was on mathematics interest inventory to suit the study on interest in basic science. The instrument was validated by experts in science education, test and measurement and basic science teacher. The instrument was pilot tested using students who were not part of the study area but shared similar characteristic with the main study. The reliability of the administered instrument using Cronbach's alpha was obtained as 0.71. The treatment group was taught using Dalton Plan Instructional Model while the control group was exposed to Conventional Lecture Method for four weeks. The data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviation for research questions and research hypotheses were tested using independent sample t-test 0.05 level of significant.

Result

Research Questions 1:

What is the impact of Dalton plan instructional Model and conventional lecture method on interest among upper basic students when taught Basic Science?

Table 1: Pre-test and Post-test Mean Interest Score of Students taught Basic Science Concept Using Dalton Plan Instructional Model and those taught using Conventional Lecture Method

Treatment	N	Pretest Mean	Std. D Pretest	Posttest Mean	Std. D Posttest	Mean Difference	Decision
Experimental	38	64.29	9.25	71.32	9.65	7.03	Significant
Control	35	59.54	9.71	61.49	7.86	1.95	

Source: *Fieldwork, 2024*

Table 1 presents the statistics pre-test and post-test mean interest scores among students taught basic science concepts, using Dalton Plan Instructional Model and the Conventional Lecture Method. The Dalton plan instructional Model group, consisting of 38 students, with their pre-test mean interest score of 64.29 (SD = 9.25) and a post-test mean interest score of 71.32 (SD = 9.65). In contrast, the Conventional Lecture Method group, comprising 35 students, exhibited a pre-test mean interest score of 59.54 (SD = 9.72) and post-test mean interest score of 61.49 (SD = 7.86). The DPIM and the CLM mean difference for the two groups are 7.03 and 1.95 respectively. This implies that the Dalton Plan Instructional Model treatment demonstrated a higher mean interest scores compared to the Conventional Lecture Method.

H0₁:

There is no significant difference in the mean interest rating score of Dalton plan instructional model and conventional lecture method among upper basic students when taught Basic Science.

Table 2: Summary of Post-test Independent Sample t-test of Students Interest Scores According to Treatment (Dalton Plan Instructional Model and Conventional Lecture Method)

Treatment	N	Mean	Std. D	Df	t-test	P-value	Decision
Experimental	38	71.32	9.65	71	4.75	.010	H ₀₆ Rejected
Control	35	61.49	7.86				

Source: *Fieldwork, 2024*

Table 2 statistics provides an independent-sample t-test conducted to compare the mean interest rating scores among students taught basic science concept using Dalton plan instructional model and those taught using Conventional lecture Method. The Dalton plan Instructional Model group, consisting of 38 students, displayed a mean interest score of 71.32 (SD = 9.65), while the Conventional Method group, comprising 35 students, had a mean interest score of 61.49 (SD = 7.86). The independent sample t-test indicated a significant difference between the two groups ($t = 4.75$, $df = 71$, $p = .010$). Consequently, the null hypothesis H₀₁, indicating difference in the interest rating scores of students taught with Dalton plan instructional Model and

the Conventional lecture Method. This implies that there was a statistically significant difference in the interest levels of students taught basic science concept using Dalton plan instructional model and those taught using Conventional lecture Method.

Discussion of Finding

Based on the outcome of the study, the summary of the finding; The result from research revealed that there was a significant mean interest rating score difference of students taught basic science concepts using Dalton Plan Instructional model and Conventional Lecture Method. This is in line with Samuel (2018) who stated that, prior to the treatment the study revealed that significant differences were found in the interest of students exposed to Simulation Instructional Package compared to that of the guided discovery method with mean scores of 73.50 and 65.12. Similarly, Gambo (2019) study indicates that there is a significant difference in the mean interest level of students in the experimental group before and after the treatment.

Conclusion

Based on the finding of the study, it was concluded that Dalton Plan Instructional Model had positive impact on interest when taught basic science among upper basic students. This implies that the use of Dalton plan Instructional Model in Basic Science would help to improve interest of students in basic science and could go a long way to reduce the poor academic performance of students especially at the Basic Education Certificate Examination.

Recommendation

Based on the finding of the study, the following recommendation was drawn: School principals through the heads of departments should encourage Basic science teachers to adopt Dalton Plan Instructional Model in the classroom as teaching method since it improved students' interest and understanding of the Basic Science subject in Kano Metropolis.

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